

ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF SERVICE PARAMETERS AND INTERCONNECTION AMONG IP NETWORKS

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Abstract:

IP specifies the technical format of packets and the addressing scheme for computers to communicate over a network. Most networks combine IP with a higher-level protocol called Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), which establishes a virtual connection between a destination and a source. When any organization wants to implement IPv6 network in their service area, it is not imaginable to implement all of a sudden in an entire area. It necessities slow migration from IPv4 to IPv6 without greatly affecting the Service. The Dual stack deployment using NAT and tunneling concept has been proposed for this migration. While IPv6 deployment from the inside of the network leading to the edges with success, the transition remains an issue today. To fill this gap, we propose a technique to provide the supporting tools and algorithms to enable this transition to become automatic and enable inbuilt security features. Based on a model of an IPv4 network, we design and implement IPv6 network and it provisions auto-configuration to the host and security is inbuilt with this protocol.

Key Words: IPv4, IPv6, Routing, Dual Stack & Network Address Translation (NAT).

1. Introduction:

In order to fill this breach and to present the essential algorithms and provide the subsidiary tools to permit this transition to become automatic. Based on the model of an IPv4 network, we design and implement an IPv6 network, thereby it supports auto configuration to the host and security is inbuilt with the protocol. Enabling the IPv6 protocol which enable the stateless auto configuration and also enables the security features which is inbuilt with IPv6 protocol. IPv4 is an abbreviation of “Internet Protocol Version Four”. It is also recognized as RFC 719. IPv4 was the fourth generation of Internet Protocol and was also the first version to be extensively deployed. The Internet Protocol sits on the third layer of the OSI network model. This is also identified as the network layer. The physical layer is the first layer in the OSI which is software based. The network layer (third layer) of the OSI model generally deals with finding, routing and switching for end to end communications that are not unswervingly connected to each other using a physical link. The security features is not in built with IPv4, ISP uses ACL, fire-wall/check point which enables the security in IPv4 network. The Internet Protocol is the most leading protocol on the Internet nowadays and commonly runs on upper layer protocols such as the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and the User Datagram Protocol (UDP). IP networking is a pattern of connectionless networking service (CLNS). IPv4 address consists of 32 bits, 4 bytes that are a combination between zeros and ones. The address contains two parts; the network and host address part.

2. Related Works in IP Networks:

Yehia et al. have planned various routing protocols and assessed them based on some performance metrics [1]. This evaluation is performed hypothetically and by using simulation. Sunjian and fang have introduced the OSPF protocol for IPv6 which is also mentioned as OSPFv3 and they primarily familiarized the knowledge of IPv6, and then implemented the OSPF over IPv6 [2]. Horenoor has introduced the implementation decision to be made when the choice is available between protocols that involve distance vector or link state or the combination of both [3]. In this paper, it is shown that OSPF definitely achieves better when compared to RIP in terms of network convergence, latency and throughput. Bahk and Zarki described about various dynamic multipath routing algorithm for networks [4]. Joseph Davies has specified detailed information for understanding IPv6 and its routing protocols [5]. The authors have made the case studies in real time about use of the dynamic routing protocols [6-8]. A tutorial has been entailed for simulating the wide area network using GNS-3 [9, 10].

3. The Addressing Format of IPV4:

The Internet Protocol version-4 (IPv4) is the fourth reconsideration in the expansion of internet protocol (IP) and the first version of the protocol to be extensively deployed. IPv4 is still by far the most extensively deployed internet layer protocol. It is basically a connectionless protocol for the use on packet switched link layer networks. It does not function on best effort delivery model, which does not guarantee delivery nor does it assure proper sequencing or avoidance of duplicate delivery.

Figure 1: IPv4 Addressing Scheme

These features including data integrity are addressed by an upper layer transport protocol such as the TCP. IPv4 uses 32 bit (4 byte) addresses which limits the address space to 4294967296(2³²) addresses. This diminishes the number of addresses that may be allocated for routing on the public internet. As addresses are assigned to the end users, IPv4 address have been developing. Network addressing changes by classful network design, classless inter-domain routing and the network address translation (NAT) have contributed to delay, significantly the inevitable exhaustion which occurred on February 3rd2011 when IANA allocated the last five blocks to the five regional internet registries (RIRs). This restriction stimulated the development of IPv6.

4. The Addressing Format of IPV6:

IPv6 or Internet Protocol Version-6 is the subsequent generation protocol for the Internet. It is intended to provide numerous advantages over the existing and current Internet Protocol Version 4 (IPv4).

Figure 2: IPv6 Addressing Scheme

Both IPv6 and IPv4 describe network layer protocol (how the data is sent from one computer to the alternative computer over packet-switched networks such as the Internet). It is consequently also called the Next Generation Internet Protocol. Though IPv6 is the successor of IPv4, both the protocol versions will endure to be data-oriented protocols for use in Internet in the fourth coming years. IPv6 addresses the chief problem of IPv4 that is the exhaustion of addresses to link computers or host in a packet switched network. IPv6 has a very hefty address space and consists of 128 bits as compared to 32 bits in IPv4. Therefore, it is now thinkable to support 2¹²⁸ unique IP addresses, a considerable increase in number of computers that can be addressed with the aid of IPv6 addressing structure. In addition, this addressing structure will also eradicate the need of NAT (network address translation) that reason to several networking problems. IPv6 addresses are represented by eight groups of hexadecimal quartets detached by colons in between them. Following is an instance of a valid IPv6 address: 2001:cdba:0000:0000:0000:0000:3257:92 address may be condensed to a single zero or altogether omitted. Consequently, the following IPv6 addresses are similar and equally valid: 2001:cdba:0000:0000:0000:0000:3257:9652 2001:cdba:0:0:0:0:3257:9652 2001:cdba::3257:9652

5. Implementation of RIP:

Figure 3: Implementation of RIP

RIP is a dynamic and distance vector routing protocol based around the Berkley BSD application routed, and was developed for minor IP based networks. RIP uses UDP port 520 for route updates. RIP computes the best route based on hop count. Like all distance vector routing protocols, RIP takes some time for converge.

While RIP necessitates less CPU power and RAM than some other routing protocols. The RIP permits that routers update their routing tables at programmable intervals, commonly every 30 seconds. One of the difficulties of routers that use RIP is that continually they are connected with routers neighboring to update his tables of routing, producing therefore a great amount of network traffic. As the number of jumps is only metric of routing used by the RIP, not essentially it selects the fastest route towards its destiny. A metric one is a measurement unit that permits making decisions and next will study that other protocols of routing use other metric ones in addition to the number of jumps to treasure the best route of data transfer.

A. RIP Characteristics:

- ✓ Distance vector routing protocol
- ✓ Uses Bellman-Ford algorithm
- ✓ It metric is the number of jumps
- ✓ The extreme number of jumps is 15
- ✓ One updates every 30 seconds.
- ✓ Not always it selects the fastest route for the packages
- ✓ It produces great amount of traffic of network with updates

B. Basic RIP Configuration:

```
router> enable
router# config t
router(config)#ipv6 unicast-routing
router(config)#ipv6 router rip bsnl
router(config-rtr)#exit
router(config)#interface ethernet 0
router(config-if)# ipv6 enable
router(config-if)# ipv6 rip bsnl enable
router(config-if)# ipv6 address 2001:1111::1/56
router(config-if)# no shut
router(config-if)# exit
```

6. The Implementation of OSPF:

In 1988, the group: Internet Engineers Task Force (IETF) commenced to develop a new-fangled protocol of routing. Then they developed the Open Shortest Path First protocol (OSPF). Open Shortest Path First (OSPF) is an adaptive routing protocol for the Internet Protocol (IP) networks. It uses a link state routing algorithm and falls into the group of interior routing protocols, functioning within a single autonomous system (AS). OSPF is an interior gateway protocol that routes the Internet Protocol (IP) packets exclusively within a single routing domain (autonomous system). It gathers link state information from obtainable routers and constructs a topology map of the network.

Figure 4: Implementation of OSPF

The topology regulates the routing table presented to the Internet Layer which makes routing decisions based exclusively on the destination IP address found in IP packets. OSPF was intended to support variable-length subnet masking (VLSM) or Classless Inter-Domain Routing (CIDR) addressing models. OSPF notices changes in the topology such as link failures, very rapidly and converges on a new loop-free routing arrangement within seconds. It calculates the shortest path tree for each route using a technique based on Dijkstra's algorithm which is a shortest path first algorithm.

A. OSPF characteristics:

- ✓ Fast detection of deviations in the topology and very fast reestablishment of routes without loops
- ✓ Lower overload, use updates that notify about changes on routes
- ✓ Division of traffic by numerous equivalent routes
- ✓ Routing according to the type of service
- ✓ Usage of multi-send in local area networks
- ✓ Subnet and the Super-net mask
- ✓ Better Authentication

B. Basic OSPF Configuration:

```
router> enable
router# config terminal
router(config)#host name router
router(config-rtr)#exit
router(config)#interface ethernet 0/0
router(config-if)# ip add 10.0.0.1 255.0.0.0
router(config-if)# no shutdown
router(config)#
routerospf 10
router(config-router)# network 10.0.0.0 0.255.255.255 area 0
router(config-router)#router-id 1.1.1.1
router(config)# no shut
router(config-if)# exit
```

7. Experimental Validation and Results:

Two IPv6 networks have been converged through IPv4 network using tunnelling perception. Manual tunneling concept has been employed here. Auto tunneling and dual stack tunnelling have been performed. The performance of these tunneling are evaluated by using Cisco Packet Tracer. Using manual tunneling, the interoperability of IPv6 and IPv4 has been checked. IPv6 network routes using RIP protocol and the IPv4 network routes using OSPF.

8. Conclusion and Future Work:

A Classy Network Simulator Software package for the load balancing among routers was developed in GNS3. Inter-operability of IPv6 network and IPv4 network have been analysed using manual tunneling. It builds an enduring virtual link between IPv6 and IPv4 networks. It forms a static tunneling. It is manually configured, thereby it is not scalable but has a secured communication. The main objective of this research work was to realize the implementation and successful validation using the simulator. Future scope will be towards enabling the security features which is in-built with IPv6 protocol. Also deployment of IPv6 using dual stack and auto tunneling and analysing the performance using Cisco Packet Tracer will be carried out.

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